

Life-times of Excited States of Molecules and their Determination

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When a radiation of proper frequency falls on a system of oscillators, it is absorbed by them and the latter are transferred to higher energy levels according to certain rules. The oscillators cannot stay, however, at this excited energy level for an indefinite length of time and must return to the ground state. The time spent by the atom or molecule in the excited state, if unperturbed by the environment, is known as its natural radiative life-time.

This radiative life-time, T_N , is inversely related to the sum of spontaneous transition probabilities (ΣA_{ij}) of the molecule from all the vibrational levels of the upper state to those of the lower state obeying Franck-Condon principle, i.e., it is the rate constant of spontaneous emission process. Since absorption and emission are completely reversible processes, what is probable for emission must be probable for absorption; hence life-time can be equated to the probability of absorption by the given molecule.

From the classical theory of dispersion¹⁻², the transition probability is given by the oscillator strength, f , of the absorbing dipole which can be defined as the ratio of number of electrons excited to the total number of optical electrons in the system. The oscillator strength is related to the square of the transition moment integral defined by $f \propto \int \psi_i M \psi_j d\nu$, where M is the component of dipole moment vector $\Sigma e r_i$ and r_i is the vector distance of the i th electron to the origin of a co-ordinate system fixed in the molecule, and e is the electronic charge.

Various relations for states i and j are given as follows:

$$T = \frac{1}{\Sigma A_i} = \frac{1.5}{\nu_{\max}^2 \cdot \Sigma f_{ij}}$$

$$f = \frac{8 \lambda^2 m c \nu}{3 h} \cdot D$$

where $D =$ dipole strength of transition $= g Q^2 = g \cdot f \cdot \int \psi_i \cdot \Sigma r_i \psi_j \cdot d\nu$ which differs from the dipole moment integral by a factor 'e'. g is the multiplicity of the upper state and $\nu =$ frequency of maximum absorption in wave numbers per cm.

Dipole strength or oscillator strength is experimentally obtained from the intensity of absorption by the system. The integrated extinction coefficient $\int_{-\alpha}^{+\alpha} \epsilon \nu d\nu$, where the

integral gives the total strength for all the transitions between the two given states for frequency ranging from $+\infty$ to $-\infty$ is a better measure of intensity than the peak height at maximum absorption. The integration can be obtained from the area of the extinction curve for transition, plotted with wave number as abscissa. The final relation is

$$f = 4.3? \times 10^{-9} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \epsilon_{\nu} d\nu$$

By considering the thermodynamic equilibrium between radiation and matter, it has been shown that there is a relationship between the probability of radiational emission from an excited state and the strength of the absorption band^{3,4}. Expressing the magnitude of A_{ij} Einsteins coefficient for spontaneous emission in terms of mean life of the excited state ($1/T_N$), and B_{ij} Einsteins coefficient for induced emission by integrated absorption intensities, the value of T_N has been given by Lewis and Kasha⁵ by the expression

$$T_N = \frac{3.47 \times 10^8}{\nu_{\max}^2 n^2} \cdot \frac{g_u}{g_l} \int \frac{1}{\epsilon_{\nu}} d\nu$$

where $\nu_{\max}$ is the wave number for maximum absorption, n , the refractive index of the medium at that frequency, g_u and g_l , the multiplicities of the upper and lower states involved in the transition. For most transitions allowed by the selection rule, $g_u = g_l = 1$ (singlet $\rightarrow$ singlet), whereas for transitions involving change of multiplicity, $g_u = 3$, $g_l = 1$ (singlet $\rightarrow$ triplet). This differs from the expression given by Ladenburg only by refractive index correction term which is often taken to be unity.

These expressions are strictly true of the strength of a single atomic line where band widths are small. Under favourable conditions, the strength of a molecular transition can be obtained experimentally from and be defined by the integral of intensity over all the band lines⁶. It can be applied to complex molecules if empirical correction factors are introduced, leading to the correction for the spread of the transition frequency by vibrational—electronic coupling. The calibration factor generally appears to be not more than 2 and may be even much less than this. Some values obtained by Lewis and Kasha⁵ are shown in Table I, and compared with values obtained by other methods.

TABLE I

	$T_{\text{calc.}}$	$T_{\text{obs.}}$	Condition.
Rhodamin B	3.2×10^{-9}	4.2×10^{-9}	Glycerine soln. 25°.
Anthracene	2.2×10^{-8}	2.4×10^{-8}	Crystal ,,
Naphthalene	1.0×10^{-6}	0.33×10^{-6}	Crystal ,,

[The data for naphthalene were obtained by Kasha and Nauman⁷.]

An improved relationship given by Forster⁸

$$\frac{1}{T_N} = 2.88 \times 10^{-9} \cdot n^2 \int \frac{(2\nu_0 - \nu)^2}{\nu} \epsilon_{\nu} d\nu$$

where ν_0 is the wave number of approximate mirror-image reflection plane of the absorption and fluorescence spectra plotted against ν ,

The main difficulties in applying this equation to spectra of complicated molecules are:

- (i) Existence of fine vibrational peaks which introduce error in measuring the area under the absorption band.
- (ii) Bands corresponding to the transitions of interest are overlaid by those of another electronic transitions and hence a correction for this overlap becomes necessary, which may not be easy.
- (iii) Weak bands may "borrow" intensity from neighbouring strong bands, and may also "borrow" polarization direction.
- (iv) Refractive index correction is still an uncertain factor.

Many recent tests for the equation have been carried out in connection with the phosphorescence of organic compounds where some of the difficulties mentioned above are absent. For singlet $\rightarrow$ triplet absorption transition, Lewis and Kasha⁵ calculated the intensity of the expected absorption from the observed life-times of the phosphorescent states of a number of compounds. For phenazine, dibenzalacetone, *p*-dichlorobenzene and other compounds, the calculated band maxima were only slightly shorter than the observed phosphorescence band. Table II, based on McClure's study⁹, records some quantitative comparisons of agreement between observed life-times in the triplet state and those calculated from the integrated absorption strength for $S \rightarrow T$ transitions.

TABLE II

Compounds.	Life-time (sec.)	
	Obs.	Calc.
Benzene	7 ± 0.5	0.2 ± 1.5
Bromobenzene	0.001	0.0030 ± 0.0005
<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	0.00033 ± 0.0003	0.00153 ± 0.00006
<i>p</i> -Bromonaphthalene	0.021 ± 0.001	0.010 ± 0.003
<i>p</i> -Iodonaphthalene	0.0025 ± 0.0001	0.0019 ± 0.0001

The magnitude of natural radiative life-times provides important information regarding the "allowedness" of transition between two given states, which is governed by selection rules, symmetry properties, nature of excitation process, etc. Theory shows that the quantity $f_{\nu} \int \epsilon \nu d\nu$ cannot exceed $2.3 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, for a transition of one electron¹⁰ and maximum value of ϵ possible for a completely allowed transition ($f=1.0$) is about 10^5 giving natural radiative life-time equal to 10^{-9} sec. Any value less than these ideal values ($\epsilon < 10^{15}$, $f < 1$ and $T_N > 10^{-9}$ sec.) is a measure of the forbiddenness of the transition. Fig. 1 shows relationship between these quantities together with the nature of the excitation involved^{11,12}.

The values of radiative life-times T_N obtained from the integrated absorption strength will give the value of natural mean life on the assumption that all the molecules excited to the higher state return to the ground state solely by radiative process. This will be then the upper limit to mean life-times. But in an actual system, specially in the condensed state, there will be other deactivating processes, which will compete with the spontaneous emission process, thereby decreasing the value for the radiational constant. After excita-

tion to the lowest singlet state, the molecule can lose its excitation energy in one or more of the following ways:

Rate

1 Excitation.

 α_1 Fluorescence radiation. α_2 Internal conversion. α_3 Intersystem crossing. α_4 Photochemical reaction. α_5 Non-radiative energy transfer to like molecules or foreign molecules.

FIG. 1. The relation between natural radiative life-times (T_N), oscillator strength (f), extinction coefficient ($\epsilon_{\max}$) of electronic transition and nature of the corresponding absorption and emission processes.

FIG. 2. Transitions and their respective time periods in sec. giving rise to absorption and emission spectra. (a) Absorption $G \rightarrow S$, (b) $G \rightarrow S$, (c) radiationless transition $S^* \rightarrow S^*$, (d) fluorescence $S^* \rightarrow G$, (e) radiationless transition $S \rightarrow T$, (f) phosphorescence $T \rightarrow G$.

Different transitions involved are shown diagrammatically in Fig. 2, where direct lines indicate radiative transitions and the wave lines, non-radiative transitions.

The natural life-time $T_N = 1/\alpha_1$, and actual lifetime $T = \frac{1}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 + \alpha_5}$

where α 's are the probabilities of various processes. The life-time of the phosphorescent state T_p , will be determined by the probability of radiative intercombination with the ground state¹³ after intersystem crossing from the excited singlet to triplet level (α_3). The factors which will tend to reduce T_p are (a) internal conversion, i.e., non-radiative intercombination with the ground state, (b) photochemical dissociation from triplet level, (c) triplet $\rightarrow$ triplet radiationless energy transfer to nearby molecules¹⁴.

Radiative transition from an excited state to the ground state is a spontaneous process; hence all photoluminescence processes follow exponential decay law. Intensity of emission at any time t , is proportional to the number (n) of molecules in the upper state and is given by the relation:

$$I = I_0 e^{-kt},$$

where I_0 is the intensity when exciting source is cut off after the establishment of the photostationary equilibrium and k , the decay constant is equal to $1/T$. Putting $t = T$, we get

$$I = I_0 \frac{1}{e}.$$

The life-time of an emission process is then defined as the time taken for emitted intensity I to drop to $1/eth$ of its original value I_0 .

"Forbiddenness" of a transition manifests itself in the emission process as increased lifetime in the excited state. Absorptions with low transition probabilities, such as symmetry forbidden or selection rule forbidden transitions, will have longer decay time. A survey of Fig. 1 shows that selection rules are more strictly followed than the symmetry condition for the two states involved in the transition. Transition with change of multiplicity is therefore less probable, giving rise to long-lived phosphorescence phenomena. A definition of fluorescence and phosphorescence can then be given as the former involves transitions between first excited singlet to ground singlet with lifetimes ranging from 10^{-9} sec. to 10^{-4} sec., and the latter involves singlet $\rightarrow$ triplet transitions with life-times 10^{-4} sec. and greater.

The direct measurement of decay period is based on the principle of permitting the observation of luminescence for a short time, which may be varied, after the end of the excitation period. Such an apparatus was first constructed by Becquerel¹⁴. In its simplest form, it consists of a pair of rotating sectors mounted on a common shaft, so cut that on rotation, the first admits the light beam to the sample, while the second shields the sample from the detecting device. The first sector then interrupts the source beam, and the second opens and admits light from the luminescent sample to the detector. There are several modifications of the original Becquerel phosphorescope¹⁵. One of its modifications¹⁶ consists of two coaxial cylinders which can be rotated at various speeds. Outer

cylinder contains a suitable window and the inner cylinder contains the sample, solid or solution. The exciting light source and the detecting unit are placed on either side of the cylinders. During the course of rotation of cylinders, when the window faces the incident light source, the sample is excited and when in front of the detecting unit, it registers its intensity. The time between excitation and detection can be varied at will by changing the speed of rotation and complete decay curve can be plotted.

Other refinement⁹ is the use of phototube as the receiving device. The signal is applied to the *y*-axis of the oscilloscope and phosphoroscope is synchronised with the oscilloscope sweep. The oscilloscope then displays the exponential decay curve of the phosphorescence, which may be photographed. A similar method could be used with the more recently developed flash-tube techniques.

The shortest life-times that can be measured by Becquerel type phosphoroscope is 10^{-4} sec. only. For measurements of a very small decay period of the order of 10^{-9} sec., apparatuses are used, which are in principle the same as Becquerel phosphoroscope but without inertia. For this purpose, mechanical shutters are replaced by electrical devices. One of them is by using Kerr cell as superrapid time shutter. Kerr cell is a glass vessel containing highly purified nitrobenzene and two electrodes to which high voltages can be applied. The electric field causes a small degree of orientation of the liquid molecules so that the cell becomes doubly refracting like an uniaxial crystal; when it is placed in between crossed polaroids, suitably oriented, it allows the light to pass when the field is on. If rapidly oscillating voltages are applied, the cell is capable of responding by alternate transmission and extinction up to periods of 10^{-9} sec. Two such cells are used, one to admit exciting radiation and the other to pass the fluorescence from a cell of fluorescent solution. In 10^{-8} sec. light travels 300 cm. By varying the distances between the two shutters and the fluorescent substance and by proper synchronisation of the two shutters, complete decay curve can be obtained. This technique was utilized by Gaviola¹⁷ for measurement of life-times of uranin and rhodamin and study of the effect of solvent, concentration and polarization of incident radiation. An interesting modification of Gaviola's fluorimeter was devised by Szymanski.¹⁸

The Kerr cell was used to modulate the exciting light. The modulated light source, after passing through nicol prisms, was allowed to fall on a diffusely reflecting surface. The scattered radiation is then also modulated at the same frequency as the incident radiation. If the scattering substance is now replaced by a fluorescent solution, a time lag will be introduced in the emitted radiation due to finite time between absorption and emission, which by definition is the life-time of the excited state. This time lag will introduce a phase-shift, proportional to the life-time of the emitting molecule, in the modulation frequency of the emitted radiation as compared to that from a scattering surface. Szymanski¹⁸ measured the ellipticities of the secondary radiations for the two processes, one for instantaneous reflection process and the other for the luminescence process, and plotted the complete curves for different positions of the two samples. The value of *T* is, in first approximation, derived directly from the distance between the minima in the two curves. Decay periods as low as 10^{-9} sec. could be measured with this apparatus with an error of $\pm 0.2 \times 10^{-9}$ sec. For uranin solution, he obtained a value of 5.07×10^{-9} sec. for solutions in H₂O, EtOH and Bu¹OH, and 5.12×10^{-9} in glycerol.

In the last ten years much improvement has been made in the phase-shift method¹⁹ which is a very accurate method for the measurement of mean life-times. Ultrasonic waves and piezo-electric crystals are used to modulate the light source. The theoretical treatment by Bailey and Rollefson²⁰ is given below.

The differential equation for decay in intensity of fluorescence, I , is

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = -k_1 I \quad \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where k_1 is considered to be the sum of all first order rate constants such as deactivation through emission and also through other processes which are first order with respect to the activated species such as interaction with the solvent molecules or quenching by specific ions in solution.

Photo-activation occurs at a rate proportional to the intensity of exciting light. When excitation is by light, varying in periodic manner, the equation becomes

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = -k_1 I + k_2 J(t) \quad \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

where intensity of exciting light $J(t)$ may be represented as a Fourier series,

$$J(t) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \Sigma (a_n \cos n\omega t + b_n \sin n\omega t) \quad \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

where $a_0/2$ indicates the average intensity of exciting light and the second term gives the periodic variation about this average; ω is the circular frequency of modulation. The value of k_2 is determined by the absorption coefficient and concentration of the fluorescer and by the thickness of the solution used. In any given experiment it is constant. Substituting (3) in (2) we have

$$\frac{dI}{dt} + k_1 I = k_2 \left\{ \frac{a_0}{2} + \Sigma (a_n \cos n\omega t + b_n \sin n\omega t) \right\}$$

which is a linear first order equation and can be solved by usual methods giving

$$I = \frac{k_2}{k_1} \cdot \frac{a_0}{2} + k_2 \Sigma \frac{a_n (k_1 \cos n\omega t + n\omega \sin n\omega t)}{k_1^2 + n^2 \omega^2} + k_2 \Sigma \frac{b_n (k_1 \sin n\omega t + n\omega \cos n\omega t)}{k_1^2 + n^2 \omega^2} + C \cdot e^{-k_1 t}$$

By making further substitutions

$$\begin{aligned} \sin \Phi_n &= \frac{n\omega}{(k_1^2 + n^2 \omega^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad \cos \Phi_n = \frac{k_1}{(k_1^2 + n^2 \omega^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \\ I &= \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{a_0}{2} + k_2 \Sigma \frac{a_n \cos (n\omega t - \Phi_n)}{(k_1^2 + n^2 \omega^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \\ &\quad + k_2 \Sigma \frac{b_n \sin (n\omega t - \Phi_n)}{(k_1^2 + n^2 \omega^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} + C \cdot e^{-k_1 t} \quad \dots \dots \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

Thus fluorescence intensity is represented by another Fourier series plus an additional exponential term in t . This final term, however, becomes negligibly small as t becomes large compared to k_1 ($= 1/T$), and can be neglected. For a given component of exciting light

a component of the same frequency is obtained in the fluorescent light, but retarded in phase by the angle Φ_n which is related to the rate constant k_1 and to the mean life-time T by the relation:

$$\tan \Phi_n = \frac{n w}{k_1} = n w T.$$

For sinusoidally varying light, all of the coefficients a_n and b_n for $n > 1$ are zero so that only the first component of the Fourier series remains. By proper choice of time base, either a_1 or b_1 can be made equal to zero so that exciting light is

$$J(t) = \frac{a_0}{2} + a_1 \sin w't,$$

$$I = \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{a_0}{2} + \frac{k_2}{(k_1^2 + n^2 w^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \cdot a_1 \sin (w't - \Phi)$$

fluorescent intensity, and the phase relationship is given by $\tan \Phi = w$.

Light is modulated by a method described by Maercks²⁰ using ultrasonic standing waves in a liquid medium as an intermittent diffraction grating. The method of detection and measurement is similar to one suggested by Tummerman²¹

From the relationship between phase angle and life-time, it is seen that by proper choice of the frequency of modulation, the apparatus can be suited for measurement of small or large T values. Thus if two different emission processes with different life-times occur simultaneously, these can be separated.

These authors claim an accuracy of 0.1×10^{-9} sec. for their life-time values and for the first time have shown a positive variation of mean life of fluorescein anion in alkaline solution with the concentration of the fluorescer (Table III).

TABLE III

Concentration effect on life-time of fluorescein in 0.005M-KOH.

Conc.	$T \times 10^9$ sec.	Conc.	$T \times 10^9$ sec.	Conc.	$T \times 10^9$ sec.
$1.6 \times 10^{-6}M$	4.6 ± 0.1	$8.0 \times 10^{-5}M$	6.5	$3.0 \times 10^{-4}M$	7.4
8.0×10^{-6}	4.6	1.0×10^{-3}	6.6	4.0×10^{-4}	7.5
1.0×10^{-5}	5.0	2.0×10^{-4}	7.0	4.0×10^{-4}	7.7
8.0×10^{-5}	6.1	2.0×10^{-4}	7.0	5.0×10^{-4}	7.9

The usual effect of increasing concentration is to decrease the lifetime due to self-quenching. This increase is explained as due to absorption—reemission process within the system before an emitted quantum reaches the photomultiplier. A marked influence of secondary fluorescence has also been observed by Schmillen²².

Further improvements in the above technique has been made by Kromman¹⁹ (Fig. 3). A second crystal-controlled oscillator of frequency 5.2 Mcs is fed at the base of the photomultiplier receiving an impulse of 5.0 Mcs frequency, the frequency of modulation of incident radiation. The mixing of these two frequencies produces a beat frequency of 2 Kcs. The phase-shift was observed for 2 Kcs beat frequency rather than for 5 Mcs, thereby increasing the sensitivity of detection of small phase shifts due to small life-times. The apparatus was checked by measuring the speed of light and reproducible values of 2.98×10^{10} cm per sec. were obtained.

Using this improved apparatus, (accuracy $\pm 0.5 \times 10^{-9}$), the life-times of fluorescein in

FIG. 3. Block diagram of the phase shift apparatus for the measurement of actual life-times. (Bailey & Rollefson modified by Kroman.)

in KOH was measured Rohatgi²³, in various hydroxylic solvents such as water, water-glycerol, EtOH, PrⁿOH and BuⁿOH. Whereas no difference in lifetime values for these was observed by Szymanowski¹⁸, a decreasing order was obtained in the series EtOH, PrⁿOH, H₂O, BuⁿOH and glycerol, ranging from 6.57×10^{-9} to 6.19×10^{-9} (uncorrected for absorption-remission process). The order is the same as the boiling point of the solvents, indicating small solute-solvent interactions of van der Waal's type plus hydrogen bonding effect. Thus, this is a very good way of studying small molecular interactions in solution.

The phase-shift method is now widely used for obtaining improved values of decay periods of organic and inorganic compounds, in different states of aggregation. The values of anthracene has been obtained in vapour and in crystalline state by Galanin²⁴, in solution in solvent by Liebson²⁵ and Kroman¹⁹, and in solid solution with tetracene and naphthacene by Schmillen *et al.*²⁶. An exhaustive survey of life-times of substituted aromatics, specially benzene derivatives, has been done by Dikun, Petrov. and Sveshnikov²⁹. Rohde¹⁹ has also studied a number of hydrocarbons, useful in scintillation counters. Schmillen *et al.*^{19, 26, 27} have contributed towards the life-times of various dyestuffs and studied the effect of added quenchers on their decay period. Bonch-Bruvich *et al.*¹⁹ have measured the decay constants for colour centres in ionic crystals. Life-times of rare salts and ruby have also been measured²⁸,

Another important method for the measurement of decay period is from the study of depolarization of fluorescent radiation. The directional nature of light absorption implies that when a system of randomly oriented anisotropic oscillators is excited by plane polarized light, the probability of absorption will be the greatest for those molecules which are

oriented with their chromophoric group parallel to the electric vector of the incident radiation. Other molecules will have smaller probability given by $A = A_{\max} \cos^2 \alpha$, where $A_{\max}$ is the maximum probability of absorption for parallel orientation and α , angle between the vector direction and the chromophoric group. When $\alpha = 90^\circ$, i.e. for perpendicular orientation of the chromophore, the absorption probability is zero.

If the molecules do not rotate during the period between absorption and emission processes, i.e., if the molecules are embedded in a medium of infinite viscosity, the electric vector of emitted radiation will have the same orientation as the emitting oscillator. Since there are molecules of all orientation, the degree of polarization of emitted radiation will be much reduced. For a randomly oriented molecule in a medium of infinite viscosity, when observed at right angles to the direction of incidence, the intensity of emitted radiation with electric vector parallel to incident vector (I_{11}) is three times the intensity with emitted vector perpendicular to incident vector (I_1). The degree of polarization p , is then given by (Bowen and Wokes¹⁹³)

$$p = \frac{\Phi I_{11} - I_1}{I_{11} + I_1} = 0.5.$$

Therefore, the maximum value for p in a system with all orientations is 50%. This maximum value will not be observed in liquid solvents where the molecule has the possibility of rotation (time period 10^{-11} sec.) within the life-time of the excited molecule ($T = 10^{-8}$ secs.). But in viscous solvents like glycerol and ethylene glycol, the rotation of the molecule will be impeded to different degrees in proportion to the viscosity of the solvent. The extent of rotation within the life-time of the molecule will manifest itself in further depolarization of emitted radiation from its ideal value of 50%.

According to the theory developed by Smoluchowski³⁰ and by Einstein³¹, considering the Brownian movement of rotation, a spherical particle of volume V , rotates in a liquid of viscosity η in a short time Δt through an angle α . The mean value of this angle of rotation is given by

$$\Delta \alpha^{-2} = \frac{1}{3} \frac{RT}{\eta V} \Delta t$$

By inserting sufficiently short life-time T for Δt in the above equation, an expression was derived by Perrin³² and others³³, giving the reduced degree of polarisation which results from rotation of all individual resonators around statistically oriented axes, as

$$p = P_0 \frac{1}{1 + (1 - \frac{1}{3} P_0) \frac{RT}{\eta V} T}$$

where P_0 is maximum polarizability at infinite viscosity and R and T have their usual significance. Molar volume of the solution, V , can be obtained from Einstein's equation

$$\frac{\eta' - \eta}{\eta} = \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{C}{M} \cdot V$$

where η' is the viscosity of solution of conc. C g./c.c. of a substance of molecular weight M in a solvent of viscosity η . Hence V will vary from solvent to solvent.

The equation can be written as

$$\frac{1}{p} = \frac{1}{P_0} + \left(\frac{1}{P_0} - \frac{1}{3} \right) \frac{RT}{V} T$$

showing a linear relationship between $1/p$ and $1/\eta$.

If degree of polarization is measured in a number of solvents of varying viscosity, the intercept of $1/p$ against $1/\eta$ plot will give the value of $1/P_0$, and from the known values of pT/V life-time T can be calculated from the slope. The viscosity can be varied by mixing two solvents of different viscosity in different proportions, using a series of homologous compounds, by using polymerizable solvents or by changing the temperature. In the last case, not only the variation of η but that of T also should be taken into account³⁵. The viscosity is found to have a greater effect on polarization than temperature³⁶. The expression has been well verified by experimental studies on polarized fluorescence of dyes, hydrocarbons, cyanoplatinites and uranyl salts in liquid solutions.

From general considerations of the theory, it is expected that the observed degree of polarization will depend on the life-time of the molecule. If the life-time is short, polarization will be greater than for substances of longer life-times. For example, an aqueous solution of erythrosin shows strong polarization ($T \approx 10^{-9}$ sec.), whereas the fluorescence of uranyl salts is completely depolarized ($T \approx 10^{-6}$ sec.). In partially quenched solutions, the degree of polarization increases as the life-times are shortened^{37,38}.

In order to derive correct values from this expression, plausible values of V must be introduced. This value may change from solvent to solvent since it is not the volume of isolated solute molecule but the volume of molecule with its solvation envelop. Therefore, $1/p$ should be plotted against $1/\eta V$ to give correct results³⁹. The value of V was obtained by Perrin from diffusion coefficient. The values of P_0 and T , calculated by him, are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

	Fluorescent compounds						Cyanoplatinite.
	Uranin.	Erythrosin.	Resorufin.	Chlorophyll.	Quinine sulphate.	Anthracene.	
P_0	44	45	44	43	46	25	40
$T \times 10^9$	4.3	0.08	3.1	30	40	250	0.3

Furthermore, it is not always clear that the macro- and micro-viscosities are the same. Even in a very viscous solvent, molecule may have the freedom to rotate so that the value of V , obtained from diffusion coefficient data and the apparent viscosity, may give erroneous results⁴⁰. The fluorescence of uranin and rhodamin in an ether-collodion solution is depolarized to nearly the same extent as in pure ether solution⁴¹. On the other hand, solutions in 90% ordinary gelatine and those in β -gelatine show large polarization although the difference in viscosity of the two solutions is thousandfold. The important property is apparently not the viscosity of the solution, but the mobility of the molecules to which the dye is attached or on which it is adsorbed⁴².

Perrin's expression has been derived on the assumption that T is independent of viscosity. If T is a function of η , the equation cannot be applied⁴². Besides, the value of T may not be the same in different solvents employed to vary the viscosity. In such cases, relative quantum yield (Q_r) also becomes a variable and Q_r should be plotted against $Tr/\eta V$.

The degree of polarization must be measured at very low concentrations, because in concentrated solutions resonance-energy transfers of excitational energy between oscillators of different orientations will also lead to additional depolarization⁴³.

Tawde and Ramnathan⁴⁴ have shown an increase in mean life-times with increasing concentration of dyestuffs like Safranin T, Acridine Orange R., etc. These are expected to decrease again after a certain critical concentration⁴⁵.

There are some important methods for the determination of life-times of excited states of fluorescent molecules. It may be mentioned here that these life-times are for the first excited singlet (fluorescent) or lowest triplet (phosphorescent) state of the molecule only, because only these two are the emitting states. One exception is the case of azulene⁴⁶, where emission takes place from the second excited state. In general, molecules excited to higher states lose their energy by vibrational cascade and emit only from the first singlet state. So we can say that life-times of higher states are only 10^{-13} sec. or less. (Fig. 2).

It should be interesting to compare the data obtained from all these different methods. The values obtained from integrated absorption strength is although expected to give the ideal life-times T_N , there are certain uncertain factors in the calculation, such as correction for refractive index, band width, intensity borrowing, etc. Relative values should be pretty good by this method. The values from phase-shift method need corrections for various quenching effects and for errors due to overlap of absorption and emission spectra. A comparison of the values obtained from these two methods in conjunction with known values of photoluminescence efficiencies give deep insight into the nature of radiationless processes⁴⁷.

The measurement of fluorescence efficiency under conditions of equal light absorption can be related to life-times by $I_1/I_2 = T_1/T_2$. Therefore, life-times can be calculated from the quenching data⁴⁸, if the sphere of action of quenching collision can be estimated. Such an estimate is possible if one can measure the quenching and polarization in the same medium under the same conditions since the latter is influenced by the rotating Brownian motion which can only be obtained from the kinetic dimensions of the molecule. Recently Jablonski⁴⁹ has made a fresh approach to derive expressions to describe decay of photoluminescence and its dependence on polarization for molecules distributed according to the Smoluchowski distribution. A comparative study of T by different methods can reveal interesting information regarding the nature of luminescence phenomena and mechanism of its inhibition. Whether T depends on the physical state of the molecules is still a controversial question⁵⁰. In this review, stress has been given mainly on the condensed system. Importance of life-time data is increasing because of increasing use of fluorescent substances as scintillation counters and in other industrial and theoretical applications. Fluorescent compounds may show different characteristics under high energy excitation⁵¹. An exhaustive review of properties of fluorescent compounds used as scintillators is given by Sangster *et al*⁵².

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